

MIXED SHELL ELEMENTS FOR INCOMPRESSIBLE VISCOELASTIC DIELECTRIC ELASTOMERS

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Abstract. The focus of this work lies on modeling and simulation of thin dielectric viscoelastic structures undergoing large deformations of 100% and beyond. A shell formulation is developed that incorporates the necessary kinematic and constitutive features to capture the structure's characteristics under transient electric loads. This includes the incorporation of not only elastic and viscous membrane strains and curvature, but also thickness deformation and variation of the electric field through the thickness. A model based on the second principle of thermodynamics is presented, which is then discretized using low-regularity shell elements in a variational setting. Computational results prove the accuracy and efficiency of the proposed method.

Keywords: Dielectric shell; Viscoelasticity; Mixed formulation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The usage of electro-active polymers in smart structures is increasing, not least due to their ability to undergo deformations beyond 100% under electric stimulation. However, accurate modeling of their behavior remains a significant challenge as it involves the interplay of mechanical, electrical and viscoelastic effects. Within this work, we focus on modeling the elastic and viscous characteristics of thin dielectric plates.

When designing a dielectric actuator, compliant electrodes are placed on the surfaces of a thin, often pre-stretched structure. Under application of an electric voltage, electrodes are pulled towards each other due to Maxwell stresses in the dielectric material; the structure contracts in thickness direction. For an incompressible elastomer, this change in thickness implies in-plane extension, which is used for actuation. Such concepts have been proposed and modeled e.g. by Klinkel et al. [1] or Kadapa and Hossain [2], see also the review on soft robotics by Gu et al. [3]. Often, these elastomers are modeled purely elastic. Several authors have proposed to include viscoelastic relaxation to obtain more accurate results; we cite Bishara and Jabareen [4] and Mehnert et al. [5].

When discretizing thin structures using a volumetric finite element mesh, continuum mechanics material models can be transferred to the computational method directly. However, locking effects are expected in computations in view of the thin-walled nature of structures. Several authors have proposed techniques to alleviate or circumvent these problems; see e.g. solid shell elements proposed by Klinkel et al. [1], solid elements developed by Kadapa and Hossain [2] or mixed solid elements introduced by Pechstein [6]. As an alternative, structural elements based on plate or shell formulations have been developed. We cite non-exhaustively isogeometric shell elements proposed by Kiendl et

al. [7] or Duong et al. [8], and large deformation plate elements by Staudigl et al. [9]. In the context of dimensional reduction, a proper transition from three-dimensional continuum modeling to a structural formulation is crucial. None of the relevant aspects, which in this case include through-the-thickness distributions of thickness strains and electric field, can be neglected, as has been analyzed recently by Pechstein and Krommer [10].

In the current contribution, we develop a shell formulation that incorporates the necessary kinematic and constitutive features to capture the behavior of thin viscoelastic dielectric structures under transient electric loads. We develop a thermodynamically consistent model based on the free energy density and a dissipation function imposing the kinematic assumptions of Kirchhoff-Love shells, which integrates the viscoelastic constitutive model with electrostatic field equations, based on prior work addressing elastic incompressible dielectric shells [10].

A mixed shell element implementing this formulation is proposed, which extends the element proposed in [10] adding viscoelastic internal strains. The element originally introduced in [11] for St. Venant-Kirchhoff materials has been shown to be very versatile; only nodal degrees of freedom for the displacement field are necessary, such that standard shape functions can be used, and there are no restrictions on the structure of the underlying finite element mesh. Moments and curvatures enter the formulation as additional unknowns. Element-local degrees of freedom for thickness deformation and the through-the-thickness distribution of the electric field have proven to be necessary to mimic the behavior of dielectric shells correctly.

The proposed elements are validated through a benchmark problem [12] and compared against three-dimensional results. Our findings highlight the capability of the mixed shell elements to simulate the complex behavior of the electro-viscoelastically coupled material in thin shell-like structures.

The remainder of this work is organized as follows: in Section 2, a continuum model of dielectric viscoelastic materials is presented. Section 3 is dedicated to the definition of a non-according shell formulation and finite element discretization. Finally, computational results are presented in Section 4.

2 MODELING OF INCOMPRESSIBLE VISCOELASTIC DIELECTRIC MATERIALS

When modeling electroelastic materials, it is standard practice to account for the significant difference between the speed of sound and the speed of light. This large disparity justifies limiting the formulation to the electrostatic regime. Within this work, we further assume that all material velocities are sufficiently low, such that inertial forces and dynamic effects can be neglected, thereby simplifying the analysis to a quasi-static framework.

Consider a material body \mathcal{B} , for which we distinguish between its position in the reference configuration, denoted by the position vector \mathbf{X} , and its position in the current or deformed configuration, represented by the position vector \mathbf{x} . Using standard notation for all kinematic quantities, the displacement field is defined as $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{X}$. With the displacement field defined, we can introduce the deformation gradient tensor \mathbf{F} , a fundamental quantity in continuum mechanics that relates the differential change in position from the reference to the current configuration, as $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{I} + \text{Grad } \mathbf{u}$. The deformation gradient tensor does not only describe the deformation of a material body but also serves as the foundation for defining various strain measures. One important strain measure is the right Cauchy-Green tensor, denoted as \mathbf{C} , which is defined as $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \mathbf{F}$. Moreover, let $J = \det \mathbf{F}$ denote the Jacobi determinant, which describes the change of volume under deformation. For incompressible

materials, we require $J \equiv 1$ throughout \mathcal{B} .

Faraday's law ensures the existence of an electric potential Φ , such that the spatial electric field $\mathbf{e} = -\nabla_{\mathbf{x}}\Phi$ is its negative spatial gradient. With respect to the reference configuration, we define the material electric field $\boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}} = -\nabla_{\mathbf{X}}\Phi = \mathbf{F}^{-T} \cdot \mathbf{e}$.

In order to describe viscoelastic behavior, the so called generalized Maxwell model as described in [13] is used, see also Figure 1.

Figure 1: Generalized Maxwell model.

To characterize the material's properties, we use the *long term modulus* E_∞ , as well as modulus E_1 and viscosity η_1 of the Maxwell element. The instantaneous modulus of the material is then given as $E_0 = E_\infty + E_1$. As we are dealing with incompressible polymers only, Poisson's ratio is at the limit of $\nu = 0.5$, and the respective shear moduli are given by $\mu_\infty = E_\infty/3$ and $\mu_1 = E_1/3$.

In order to derive a large-deformation formulation, we use a multiplicative split in terms of the deformation gradient tensor, where we follow Ask et al. [14]. The deformation gradient tensor is split into its volumetric and isochoric part, which are defined as $J^{1/3}\mathbf{I}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{F}} = J^{-1/3}\mathbf{F}$, respectively. Accordingly, we define the isochoric part of the right Cauchy-Green tensor as $\hat{\mathbf{C}} = J^{-2/3}\mathbf{C}$.

Following Ask et al. [14], the isochoric part of the deformation gradient tensor is further decomposed into its elastic and viscoelastic part, where the viscoelastic part \mathbf{F}_V is modeled to be volume preserving,

$$\hat{\mathbf{F}} = \hat{\mathbf{F}}_e \cdot \mathbf{F}_V, \quad \text{with } \det \mathbf{F}_V \equiv 1. \quad (1)$$

This decomposition is now used in terms of the right Cauchy-Green tensor, which leads to

$$\mathbf{C}_V = \mathbf{F}_V^T \cdot \mathbf{F}_V, \quad \hat{\mathbf{C}}_e = \hat{\mathbf{F}}_e^T \cdot \hat{\mathbf{F}}_e = \mathbf{F}_V^{-T} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{C}} \cdot \mathbf{F}_V^{-1}. \quad (2)$$

We propose to use an energy-based formulation to get a thermodynamically consistent model where the free energy density Ψ is decomposed additively into three parts – the hyperelastic potential Ψ_∞ , the viscoelastic potential Ψ_1 and dielectric contributions Ψ_{diel} ,

$$\Psi = \Psi_\infty + \Psi_1 + \Psi_{diel}. \quad (3)$$

The hyperelastic potential is based on a Neo-Hookean potential including an independent pressure p , which acts as a Lagrangian multiplier for the incompressibility constraint. The viscoelastic potential Ψ_1 is also of Neo-Hooke type. The dielectric contribution, often denoted as Helmholtz free energy (augmented by vacuum contributions), is characterized through the material's electric permittivity ϵ . We list our formal choices for the different contributions,

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_\infty &= \frac{\mu_\infty}{2} (\text{tr } \mathbf{C} - 3) - \mu_\infty \log J + p \log J \\ \Psi_1 &= \frac{\mu_1}{2} (\text{tr } \hat{\mathbf{C}}_e - 3) = \frac{\mu_1}{2} (\hat{\mathbf{C}} : \mathbf{C}_V^{-1} - 3), \\ \Psi_{diel} &= -\frac{1}{2}\epsilon \mathbf{e} \cdot \mathbf{e} = -\frac{1}{2}\epsilon \boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{-1} \cdot \boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

More detailed motivation for the definition of these potentials is presented by Kunzemann et al. [15] concerning the viscoelastic modeling and Pechstein et al. [10] concerning the dielectric contribution.

The Clausius-Duhem inequality states that dissipation \mathcal{D} is non-negative (cf. [16]),

$$\mathcal{D} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{T} : \dot{\mathbf{C}} - \mathcal{D} \cdot \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} - \dot{\Psi} \geq 0, \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{T} are the second Piola-Kirchhoff stresses, defined by $\mathbf{T} = 2 \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}}$, and $\mathcal{D} = -\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ is the material dielectric displacement vector. We use a dissipation function to define dissipation in terms of the viscoelastic strain and its rate,

$$\mathcal{D} = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{C}}_V} : \dot{\mathbf{C}}_V \quad \text{with } \phi = \frac{1}{12} \eta_1 \left((\mathbf{C}_V^{-1} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{C}}_V) : (\mathbf{C}_V^{-1} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{C}}_V) \right). \quad (6)$$

For details on material modeling using dissipation functions, we refer interested readers to [17]; the present choice for ϕ is discussed in [15]. With these considerations, we can write the principle of virtual work for the multiplicative decomposition of the deformation gradient tensor as

$$\int_B \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}} : \delta \mathbf{C} + \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \mathbf{C}_V} : \delta \mathbf{C}_V + \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial p} \delta p + \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} : \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \right) dV + \int_B \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{C}}_V} : \delta \dot{\mathbf{C}}_V dV = \delta W_{ext}. \quad (7)$$

Above, the first integral collects the virtual work of internal forces, while the second term on the left hand side corresponds to the dissipated work. Using common notation, δW_{ext} collects all virtual work contributions from external loads.

3 Shell formulation

The approach outlined above for describing the behavior of viscoelastic dielectric materials will now be applied to shells and plates, assuming the principles of the Kirchhoff-Love shell theory. Following the notation of Vetyukov [18], we denote the shell's midsurface as \mathcal{S} in the reference configuration with its normal vector \mathbf{N} and t as the shell's thickness. The volumetric shell domain is defined as $\Omega_S = \{\mathbf{R} + \zeta \mathbf{N} : \mathbf{R} \in \mathcal{S} \text{ and } \zeta \in (-t/2, t/2)\}$. Using the normal vector \mathbf{N} , we can define the first metric tensor as $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{N}\mathbf{N}$ and the second metric tensor as $\mathbf{B} = -\nabla_S \mathbf{N}$, where ∇_S denotes the surface nabla operator. These metric tensors are essential for describing the shell's geometry and deformation. Within this contribution, we restrict the derivations to the case of initially plane structures, where $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{0}$.

Introducing the midsurface displacement as \mathbf{u}_S , such that $\mathbf{r} := \mathbf{R} + \mathbf{u}_S$ represents the position of the midsurface of the shell after deformation, we can define the surface deformation gradient as $\mathbf{F}_S = (\nabla_S \mathbf{r})^T = \mathbf{A} + (\nabla_S \mathbf{u}_S)^T$. It should be noted that this tensor is not invertible, as it is only of rank two.

Following [11], the normal vector of the deformed midsurface can be expressed by using the well-defined cofactor tensor of \mathbf{F}_S , which leads to

$$\mathbf{n} = \frac{\text{Cof } \mathbf{F}_S \cdot \mathbf{N}}{|\text{Cof } \mathbf{F}_S \cdot \mathbf{N}|}. \quad (8)$$

The two metric tensors can be defined not only for the reference configuration but also for the deformed configuration, as $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{n}\mathbf{n}$ and $\mathbf{F}_S^T \cdot \mathbf{b} = -\nabla_S \mathbf{n}$. We once again follow the work of [18] to

introduce the two Green strain measures of the shell surface, the symmetric membrane strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ and the symmetric curvature tensor $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$,

$$\begin{aligned}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} &= \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{F}_S^T \cdot \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{F}_S - \mathbf{A}), \\ \boldsymbol{\kappa} &= - (\mathbf{F}_S^T \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{F}_S - \mathbf{B}) = \mathbf{F}_S^T \cdot \nabla_S \mathbf{n} - \nabla_S \mathbf{N}.\end{aligned}\tag{9}$$

Following the assumptions from Pechstein et al. [10], the deformation kinematics are assumed to be free of shear, but including thickness strains. An according mapping of material to spatial point can be formulated using not only the midsurface displacement \mathbf{u}_S , but also the thickness coordinate z ,

$$\mathbf{R} + \zeta \mathbf{N} \mapsto \mathbf{R} + \mathbf{u}_S + z(\zeta) \mathbf{n}.\tag{10}$$

When neglecting higher order contributions through the thickness, the right Cauchy-Green tensor of such a deformation is found as

$$\mathbf{C}_3 = \mathbf{C}_2 + C_{NN} \mathbf{N} \mathbf{N}, \quad \text{with } \mathbf{C}_2 = \mathbf{A} + 2(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + z \boldsymbol{\kappa}) \text{ and } C_{NN} = \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial \zeta} \right)^2.\tag{11}$$

A similar approach is chosen to discretize the viscoelastic tensor \mathbf{C}_V in terms of viscoelastic membrane strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_V$ and viscoelastic curvature tensor $\boldsymbol{\kappa}_V$. The kinematic incompressibility constraint determines the thickness contribution $C_{V,NN}$ directly,

$$\mathbf{C}_{V,3} = \mathbf{C}_{V,2} + C_{V,NN} \mathbf{N} \mathbf{N}, \quad \text{with } \mathbf{C}_{V,2} = \mathbf{A} + 2(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_V + \zeta \boldsymbol{\kappa}_V) \text{ and } C_{V,NN} = \frac{1}{\mathbf{N} \cdot \text{Cof } \mathbf{C}_{V,2} \cdot \mathbf{N}}\tag{12}$$

These tensor fields \mathbf{C}_3 and $\mathbf{C}_{V,3}$ are then used in the hyperelastic and dielectric potentials. Note that the Jacobi determinant is computed as $J = \sqrt{\det \mathbf{C}_3}$. As proposed in [10], we adopt a linear approximation for both the independent pressure $p(\zeta)$ and independent stretch $z'(\zeta) = \frac{\partial z(\zeta)}{\partial \zeta}$, ensuring that both quantities maintain the same approximation order.

Concerning the electric field, it is implicitly assumed that the structure is electroded at the both surfaces, and an external voltage V is applied. The material electric field $\boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}}$ is then oriented in direction of the surface normal \mathbf{N} , its nominal value computed as $\mathcal{E}_0 = V/t$. In the studies presented in [10], it was shown that a linear variation of the electric field has to be included in the model to capture the electromechanic interactions correctly; in the shell formulation, the electric field is finally described as

$$\boldsymbol{\mathcal{E}} = \mathcal{E}_0 (1 + \zeta \kappa_{\mathcal{E}}) \mathbf{N}.\tag{13}$$

We can now use these definitions to introduce the hyperelastic potential for the shell structure. Similar to the approach for dielectric elastomer plates as used by [9], we formulate the thermodynamic potential by using through-the-thickness integration as

$$\Psi_S(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, \boldsymbol{\kappa}, z, p, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_V, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_V, \kappa_{\mathcal{E}}) = \int_{-t/2}^{t/2} \Psi d\zeta.\tag{14}$$

We also apply integration over the thickness for the dissipation function, which results in the following relationship

$$\phi_S(\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_V, \dot{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}_V, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_V, \boldsymbol{\kappa}_V) = \int_{-t/2}^{t/2} \phi \, d\zeta. \quad (15)$$

Based on the assumptions and derivations outlined above, it is now possible to propose the principle of virtual work analogous to the one previously developed for the continuum model above, as

$$\int_S \underbrace{\left(\frac{\partial \Psi_S}{\partial \mathbf{C}_3} : \delta \mathbf{C}_3 + \frac{\partial \Psi_S}{\partial \mathbf{C}_{V,3}} : \delta \mathbf{C}_{V,3} + \frac{\partial \Psi_S}{\partial p} \delta p + \frac{\partial \Psi_S}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} : \delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \right)}_{\delta \Psi_S} dS + \int_S \frac{\partial \phi_S}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{V,3}} : \delta \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{V,3} dS = \delta W_{ext}. \quad (16)$$

However, we refer to [11], where they suggested a different approach. They propose introducing the moment tensor as an additional unknown, which acts as a Lagrangian multiplier in the defining relation of the curvature tensor. Additionally, the curvature tensor itself is discretized separately, a method recently presented by [19], which is similar to the well-known Hellinger-Reissner mixed formulation in continuum mechanics. As discussed in [10], this formulation can be extended to nonlinear hyperelasticity and electromechanically coupled problems. The resulting formulation amounts to

$$\int_S \left(\delta \Psi_S + \frac{\partial \phi_S}{\partial \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{V,3}} : \delta \dot{\mathbf{C}}_{V,3} \right) dS + \int_S \delta \left(\left(\mathbf{F}_S^T \cdot (\nabla_S \mathbf{n})^T - \nabla_S \mathbf{N} - \boldsymbol{\kappa} \right) : \mathbf{m} \right) dS = \delta W_{ext}. \quad (17)$$

Without going into the details of the implementation of the presented theory in the context of the finite element method, we refer to [10], which contains the basic ideas and properties of the finite element discretization and the shell elements used for the analysis.

4 NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

A geometrically simple example from the literature (cf. [12]), a dielectric membrane, is used to validate the present formulation. As described in [12], the membrane is analyzed without pre-stretching. The circular membrane has a thickness of H and radius A .

As shown in Figure 2, the lateral boundary is simply supported. In the shell model, this means that the displacements of the midsurface are constrained to zero in all three spatial directions. In contrast, in the continuum model, the displacements are constrained along the centerline of the lateral surface, as indicated and the mean value of the displacement in Z -direction on the lateral surface is constrained to zero.

Figure 2: Initial state of the dielectric membrane.

Within this numerical example, we assume the material to be perfectly isotropic and incompressible with $\mu_\infty = \mu_1 = 1 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and $\eta_1 = E_1 \tau_1 = 3\mu_1 \tau_1$ with $\tau_1 = 5 \text{ ms}$. Additionally we use $\epsilon = 5\epsilon_0$ as the material's permittivity.

Two different external loads are considered in the analysis. First, the membrane is subjected to an external pressure. Second, an electrical voltage is applied across its thickness direction as shown in Figure 3. As shown in [12], beyond a critical pressure $p_{ext} = p_{crit}$, no equilibrium condition can be found. This critical pressure is calculated as $p_{crit} = 2\mu_\infty \frac{H}{A}$. A characteristic electric voltage is also used for the electrical loading, which is defined as $V^* = H \left(\frac{2\mu_\infty}{\epsilon} \right)^{1/2}$. For comparison, the vertical displacement of the midpoint is expressed in a dimensionless form as u_Z/A and the time is presented dimensionless as t/τ_1 .

Figure 3: Deformed state of the dielectric membrane.

The computational results for the proposed elements are presented and compared to the solution of the corresponding fully coupled continuum problem. In addition to this comparison, the results obtained using our formulation are evaluated against existing results reported in the literature. This comprehensive comparison serves to validate the accuracy and applicability of the proposed method.

As shown below, the evolution of the vertical displacement of the the membrane's midpoint u_Z is used for a first comparison. The external loads were both applied in 5 steps. We are using the data of [12] as reference for the proposed formulation.

Figure 4: Evolution of u_Z under several different voltages, while $p_{ext} = 0.5p_{crit}$ is kept constant.

As shown in Figure 4 above, the results are in good agreement with the reference values from [12]. For 10% and 20% of V^* , both, the continuum model and the shell model, align almost perfectly with the reference values. As the voltage increases, the membrane becomes unstable and no equilibrium state can be found, which was also discussed in [12]. The numerical results exhibit exactly this behaviour, showing that the shell model is more robust in the direction of instability. Unlike the continuum model, it is unable to find an equilibrium position at later times. For 30% of V^* , the continuum model fails at $7.9\tau_1$, whereas the shell models reaches $21.5\tau_1$. For 40% of V^* , although the time difference is smaller, it remains significant: the continuum model fails at $1.5\tau_1$, whereas the shell model reaches $2.8\tau_1$.

The evolution of the membrane's shape for two different electrical voltages is shown in Figure 5. Obviously, the numerical results from the shell model were employed for this analysis as the continuum model fails to achieve an equilibrium state at 30% of V^* , even before $t/\tau_1 = 10$. These results once again show good agreement with the reference values from the original work already mentioned several times [12].

Figure 5: Evolution of the membrane's shape at two different voltages (top: $V = 0.2V^*$ and bottom: $V = 0.3V^*$).

For the special choice of geometric properties with $A = 10$ mm and $H = 0.2$ mm, the mesh of the full three-dimensional problem comprises 1331 third-order elements, with two elements across the thickness, which leads to 29679 coupling degrees of freedom in total. In comparison, the surface mesh used for the shell model consists of 55 third-order triangular elements, resulting in 2421 coupling degrees of freedom in total.

The shell's mesh illustrating an exemplary result is shown below in Figure 6. The 55 third-order elements of this very coarse mesh are clearly recognizable, yet it delivers highly accurate results consistent with those found in the literature. The efficiency of this coarse mesh highlights the potential of the presented shell elements to reduce computational effort without sacrificing the accuracy of the numerical solution.

Figure 6: Numerical result for 20% of V^* , illustrated $|\varepsilon_V|$ on the undeformed mesh (left) in the x-y-plane and on the deformed mesh (right) in the x-z-plane.

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